

**DIAGENETIC EVOLUTION OF THE NEOPROTEROZOIC
BHANDER SANDSTONE OF VINDHYAN BASIN, CHAMBAL
VALLEY, RAJASTHAN, INDIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR
PARAGENESIS AND BASIN ANALYSIS**

DISSERTATION

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Certificate

This is to certify that work entitled “*Diagenetic Evolution of the Neoproterozoic Bhandar Sandstone of Vindhyan Basin, Chambal Valley, Rajasthan, India: Implications for Paragenesis and Basin Analysis*” embodied in this dissertation is the work done by *Athar Nisar Padder* under my supervision at the *Department of Geology, Aligarh Muslim University* and is suitable in partial fulfilment for the award of *M.Sc. Degree in Applied Geology*.

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Declaration

I, *Athar Nisar Padder*, Department of Geology, certify that the work embodied in this dissertation is my bonafide work carried out by me under the supervision of *Dr. Mohammad Adnan Quasim*, at Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh. The matter embodied in this dissertation has not been submitted for the award of any other degree.

Date: 27/May/2025

Athar Nisar Padder

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Chapter 1

1. Introduction

Diagenesis comprises a broad spectrum of physical, chemical and biological post-depositional processes by which original sedimentary assemblages and their interstitial pore waters react in an attempt to reach textural and geochemical equilibrium with their environment (Curtis, 1977; Burley *et al.*, 1985). These processes are continually active as the ambient environment evolves in terms of temperature, pressure and chemistry during the deposition, burial and uplift cycle of basin history. As such, diagenesis encompasses a broad spectrum of post-depositional modifications to sediments. It ranges from weathering in subaerial environments and oxidation in the water column, includes compaction and lithification of sediments during burial, and eventually grades through a continuum into low-temperature metamorphism. In both humid and arid climates where geochemical reactions approach completion, gibbsite, kaolin group minerals and smectites form from aluminosilicate precursors. In cooler, temperate climates a greater variety of clay minerals occurs in weathering profiles reflecting metastable, intermediate breakdown products of aluminosilicates. Diagenesis is differentiated from metamorphism by a variety of mineral and thermal-history indices, but broadly a temperature transition of 180–250°C is thought to separate the two regimes.

1.1 Stages of diagenesis

Various authors have suggested that sediments go through three to six stages of diagenesis. Perhaps the most widely accepted stages of diagenesis are those proposed by Choquette and Pray (1970). Eodiagenesis refers to the earliest stage of diagenesis, which takes place at very shallow depths (a few meters to tens of meters) largely under the conditions of the depositional environment. Mesodiagenesis is diagenesis that takes place during deeper burial, under conditions of increasing temperature and pressure and changed pore-water compositions. Telodiagenesis refers to late-stage diagenesis that accompanies or follows uplift of previously buried sediments into the regime of meteoric waters. Sedimentary rocks that are still deeply buried in depositional basins have not, of course, undergone telodiagenesis. The most important diagenetic processes that take place in each of these diagenetic regimes, and the effects of these processes, are summarized in Table 01.

Table 01: Principal diagenetic processes and changes that occur in siliciclastic sedimentary rocks during burial

	Diagenetic stage	Diagenetic process	Results
Burial ↓	Eodiagenesis	Organic reworking (bioturbation)	Destruction of primary sedimentary structures; formation of mottled bedding and other traces
		Cementation and replacement	Formation of pyrite (reducing environments) or iron oxides (oxidizing environments); precipitation of quartz and feldspar overgrowths, carbonate cements, kaolinite, or chlorite
	Mesodiagenesis	Physical compaction	Tighter grain packing; porosity reduction and bed thinning
		Chemical compaction (pressure solution)	Partial dissolution of silicate grains; porosity reduction and bed thinning
		Cementation	Precipitation of carbonate (calcite) and silica (quartz) cements with accompanying porosity reduction
		Dissolution by pore fluids	Solution removal of carbonate cements and silicate framework grains; creation of new (secondary) porosity by preferential destruction of less stable minerals
		Mineral replacement	Partial to complete replacement of some silicate grains and clay matrix by new minerals (e.g., replacement of feldspars by calcite)
Clay mineral anthogenesis	Alteration of one kind of clay mineral to another (e.g., smectite to illite or chlorite, kaolinite to illite)		
Uplift ↑	Telodiagenesis	Dissolution, replacement, oxidation	Solution of carbonate cements, alteration of feldspars to clay minerals, oxidation of iron carbonate minerals to iron oxides, oxidation of pyrite to gypsum, solution of less stable minerals (e.g., pyroxenes, amphiboles)

1.2 Diagenetic processes and effects (Boggs, 2006, p. 147)

1.2.1 Eodiagenesis (Shallow burial)

The principal diagenetic changes that take place in the eogenetic regime include reworking of sediments by organisms (bioturbation), minor compaction and grain repacking, and mineralogical changes. Organisms rework sediment at or near the depositional interface through various crawling, burrowing, and sediment-ingesting activities. Bioturbation can destroy primary sedimentary structures such as lamination and create in their place a variety of traces that may include mottled bedding, burrows, tracks, and trails. Organic reworking commonly has little effect on the mineralogical and chemical composition of sediments. Owing to very shallow burial depth, sediments undergo only very slight compaction and grain rearrangement during early diagenesis.

Early diagenesis does bring about some important mineralogical changes in siliciclastic sediments. Most of these changes involve the precipitation of new minerals. In marine environments where reducing (low-oxygen) conditions can prevail, the formation of pyrite is particularly characteristic. Pyrite may form cement or may replace other materials such as woody fragments. Other important reactions include formation of chlorite, glauconite (greenish iron-silicate grains), illite/smectite clays, and iron oxides in oxygenated water zones (e.g., red clays on the deep ocean floor); and precipitation of potassium feldspar overgrowths, quartz overgrowths, and carbonate cements. In nonmarine environments, where oxidizing conditions commonly prevail, little pyrite forms. Instead, iron oxides (goethite, hematite) are commonly produced, creating redbeds. Formation of kaolinitic clay minerals and precipitation of quartz and calcite cements may take place also in this environment.

1.2.2 Mesodiagenesis (Deep burial)

Compaction: The load pressure caused by deeper burial bring about a significant increase in the tightness of grain packing with concomitant loss of porosity and thinning of beds. Increased pressure at the contact point between grains increases the solubility of the grains at the contact, leading to partial dissolution of the grains. This process is referred to as pressure solution or chemical compaction. Chemical compaction further reduces porosity and increases bed thinning. Thus, under the influence of physical and chemical compaction, aided by cementation, the primary porosity of both sands and muds is reduced dramatically during deep burial. Compaction also causes bending of flexible grains such as micas and squeezing of soft grains such as rock fragments. Mechanical compaction and pressure solution are particularly effective at depths less than 2 km, as reported by (Stone and Siever (1996)), while porosity loss at greater depths is mainly attributed to quartz cementation. (Worden and Burley (2003)) indicate that some compaction-related porosity loss can occur even at depths of up to 5 km. Additionally, compaction can cause deformation of flexible grains, such as micas, and squeezing of softer materials like rock fragments.

Chemical Processes and Changes: During deep burial, an increase in temperature by 10°C can significantly accelerate chemical reaction rates, potentially doubling or tripling them. This can destabilize mineral phases that were previously stable in the depositional

environment. Higher temperatures favor the formation of denser, less hydrous minerals and enhance the solubility of most minerals, except for carbonates, which tend to precipitate.

As burial depth increases, silicate minerals are more likely to dissolve, while a decrease in pH (increased acidity) can lead to the dissolution of carbonates. For instance, organic material decomposition releases CO₂, lowering pH and promoting carbonate dissolution. Increased pressure during burial also enhances mineral solubility at contact points, contributing to partial dissolution and releasing silica into pore waters, which can later precipitate as new silicate minerals. Key chemical processes in siliciclastic sedimentary rocks during deep burial include cementation, dissolution-replacement, and clay-mineral authigenesis. These processes are critical for understanding diagenetic changes in sedimentary environments.

Cementation: Cementation involves the precipitation of minerals into sediment pore spaces, reducing porosity and causing lithification. Common cements include carbonate (mainly calcite, with aragonite, dolomite, siderite, and ankerite being less common) and silica (quartz overgrowths, microcrystalline quartz, or opal). Other cements like clay minerals, feldspars, iron oxides, pyrite, anhydrite, and zeolites can also form. Carbonate cementation is favored by higher calcium carbonate concentrations and burial temperatures but is inhibited by increased CO₂ levels from organic decomposition, which makes pore waters acidic and corrosive to carbonates. Cement may concentrate around objects like fossils, forming concretions or globular masses. Rarely, large crystals of calcite, barite, or gypsum can envelop sand grains as "sand crystals."

Silica cement typically occurs as quartz overgrowths on existing grains, particularly in quartz arenites. This process is favored by high silica concentrations and low temperatures. Silica can be sourced locally from pressure solution or dissolution of siliceous fossils (e.g., diatoms) or imported during fluid flow linked to deep-basin dehydration or tectonic activity. Quartz cementation often occurs in basins where silica-rich waters circulate deeply at high temperatures and rise to cooler basin edges.

Dissolution: During deep burial, the dissolution of framework silicate grains and previously formed carbonate cements can occur under conditions opposite to those required for cementation. For example, carbonate minerals dissolve in cooler pore waters with high CO₂ partial pressures, while rock fragments and less stable silicate minerals (like plagioclase feldspars, pyroxenes, and amphiboles) may dissolve due to increasing burial

temperatures and organic acids in the pore waters. This selective dissolution of less stable grains during diagenesis is known as intrastratal solution.

The dissolution process increases porosity, particularly in sandstones. Petroleum geologists now recognize that much of the porosity in sandstones below a burial depth of about 3 km is secondary porosity created by these dissolution processes.

Mineral replacement: Mineral replacement is a process in which one mineral dissolves while another precipitates simultaneously in its place, typically without any change in volume. This mechanism allows the preservation of delicate textures from the original mineral, as commonly observed in petrified wood and carbonate fossils replaced by chert. Notable replacement events include the substitution of carbonate minerals by microcrystalline quartz (chert), chert by carbonate minerals, feldspars and quartz by carbonate minerals, feldspars by clay minerals, clay matrix by carbonate minerals, and albitization, where calcium-rich plagioclase is replaced by sodium-rich plagioclase. Replacement may be partial or complete; complete replacement obliterates the identity of the original minerals, which can mislead interpretations of the rock's original mineralogy. Moreover, replacement influences porosity, particularly when framework grains are replaced by clay minerals that typically reduce pore space.

Additionally, one type of clay mineral can alter to another during diagenesis. For example, smectite can transform into illite at temperatures between 55–200°C, often accompanied by water release, a process known as shale dewatering. Smectite may also convert to chlorite in a similar temperature range, while kaolinite typically alters to illite at 120–150°C. These diagenetic processes contribute to changes in clay-mineral abundance with age.

1.2.3 Telodiagenesis (Uplift)

Sedimentary rocks that have undergone deep burial diagenesis may subsequently be uplifted by mountain-building activities and unroofed by erosion. These processes bring mineral assemblages, including new minerals formed during mesogenesis, into an environment of lower temperature and pressure and in which mesogenetic pore waters are flushed and replaced by oxygen-rich, acidic meteoric (rain) waters of low salinity. Under these changed conditions, previously formed cements and framework grains may undergo dissolution (creating secondary porosity) or alteration of framework grains to clay minerals,

e.g., potassium feldspar to kaolinite (reducing porosity). Alternatively, depending upon the nature of the pore waters, silica or carbonate cements can be precipitated. Other changes may include oxidation of iron carbonate minerals and other iron-bearing minerals to form iron oxides (goethite and hematite), oxidation of sulfides (pyrite) to form sulfate minerals (gypsum) if calcium is present in pore waters, and dissolution of less stable minerals such as pyroxenes and amphiboles. The processes of telogenesis grade into those of subaerial weathering as sedimentary rocks are exposed at Earth's surface.

1.3 Significance of diagenetic studies

The study of sandstone diagenesis is relatively innovative, having grown from the description of grain shapes and textures coupled with the analysis of the evolution of bulk sediment composition with increasing depth and temperature of burial. The importance of sandstone diagenesis as a subject is evidenced by the explosive growth of both pure and applied research in this subject through the 1980s and 1990s.

This was largely driven by the petroleum industry because the amount and distribution of porosity in sandstones controls hydrocarbon migration pathways in the subsurface and, ultimately, the production of oil and gas from reservoirs. Prediction of porosity ‘sweet spots’ became a goal of explorationists world-wide in the 1980s–1990s (Curtis, 1983; Surdam *et al.*, 1984). The construction of predictive reservoir-flow-simulation models required detailed reservoir characterization based on an understanding of detrital and authigenic mineralogy (Hurst, 1987).

1.4 Significance of the study area — Vindhyan basin

The hydrocarbon potential of the Vindhyan Basin has gained attention due to its favorable tectono-sedimentary evolution and organic-rich sequences.

The Vindhyan Basin, particularly in areas like Jabara, Damoh, and Hatta, is characterized by thick sequences of black shales and sandstones that serve as source and reservoir rocks. Recent discoveries, such as gas flows from Jardepahar Porcellanite, highlight the deeper hydrocarbon plays in this region. The Jabera and Damoh grabens are critical depocenters, with seismic and well data confirming the presence of Bijawar Group rocks beneath Lower Vindhyan sequences (Suyash *et al.*, 2019). Structural features like grabens (e.g., Damoh and Jabera grabens) provide traps for hydrocarbons (Zadeh *et al.*, 2010), while secondary

porosities in formations like dolomitic limestone enhance reservoir quality. Evidence from exploratory wells, such as Jabera-1, which flowed gas at 4000 m³/day, underscores the basin's commercial viability for hydrocarbon exploration (Bhat *et al.*, 2012).

Diagenetic studies are pivotal for evaluating reservoir quality in the Vindhyan Basin. Rowsell and de Swardt (1976) emphasized that diagenetic processes such as cementation, compaction, and fracturing significantly influence porosity and permeability in Proterozoic and Paleozoic reservoirs. Similarly, Dayal *et al.* (2014) reported that Vindhyan sediments exhibit high maturation levels conducive to dry gas generation. Understanding the diagenetic history can reveal patterns of mineral replacement and dissolution that impact reservoir characteristics. This knowledge is essential for predicting where hydrocarbons may accumulate (sweet spots) and how they might be extracted efficiently. By integrating diagenetic insights with geological data from wells like Jabera, Damoh, and Hatta, geologists can better assess the viability of hydrocarbon resources in the basin and optimize exploration strategies.

1.4.1 Hydrocarbon potential of Vindhyan basin

The Vindhyan basin has considerable sediment thickness upto a maximum of 5250 m. The geothermal gradient in the basin is greater than 70 mW m⁻² and based on that the basin is categorized under medium to good prospect zone for hydrocarbon generation (Panda, 1985). Limestone and sandstone sequences can form good reservoir rocks due to the development of fracture and secondary porosities. Presence of lithological units, which can act as effective caprocks are reported by Chakrabarti (Chakrabarti, 1998). In Upper Vindhyan, cap rock conditions are better than in Lower Vindhyan due to the presence of alternating shale, sandstone, and limestone sequences. The unconformity between Lower and Upper Vindhyan may act as a seal rock. The structures along the Son Narmada lineament and series of step faults along the southeastern boundary of Bundelkhand massif may act as favorable locales for hydrocarbon accumulation. Tectonically, Vindhyan basin is comparable to Proterozoic basins of Russia (Lena Tunguska) and Australia (Amadeus), which are producing. The geochemical studies of Vindhyan equivalent rocks from Ganga basin revealed the occurrence of green colored amorphous organic matter with algal filaments (type II kerogen) capable of hydrocarbon generation. Considerable TOC content (upto 8.08% in Kajarahat Limestone, 6.43% in Bijaigarh Shale, 1.09% in carbonaceous shales) and organic carbon distribution (C_{org.} upto 1.76% in the limestone and shale sequences in both Upper and Lower Vindhyan) suggests the development of potential

source rocks in Vindhyan (Srivastava et al., 1983). The sediments show the organic maturity level well within wet to dry gas generation limit. The wetness studies of absorbed C₁ to C₆ hydrocarbons (20.77 - 97.11%) and the Thermal Alteration Index values (3.0 – 3.5) of the Vindhyan equivalent sediments in Ganga basin (Puranpur-2 well), show a maturity level within the active oil and gas generation limit (oil window) (Srivastava et al., 1983). The sediments extending in the northern part below the alluvium can have better hydrocarbon generation potential. Isotopic studies carried out by Kumar, et al., 2000, 2002 have shown that the carbonate rocks of the Nagod Formation of the Bhandar Group are characterized by marked positive $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signatures (4.1 ± 0.9 ‰ V-PDB) suggesting higher organic productivity / burial. The gently dipping Nagod Formation carbonates of Bhandar Group (Upper Vindhyan) are generally exposed on the surface, however, if sufficient sediment cover overlies these carbonates, as may be the case of Indo-Gangetic alluvial terrain, they can form good source rock for hydrocarbon generation. National Geophysical Research Institute (NGRI) in association with Directorate General of Hydrocarbons (DGH) has carried out a reconnaissance survey for surface geochemical prospecting for hydrocarbons in the western part of Vindhyan basin (Chambal Valley) and reported that the region in and around Baran-Jhalawar-Bhanpura-Garot may form a warm area for future hydrocarbon exploration (Unpublished Tech. Rep. No. NGRI-2002-Exp-361). Krishnan, 1997, recorded that the lower Vindhyan shales have geochemical parameters with possible source-rock potential.

All the above features confirm that Vindhyan sediments have necessary potential for hydrocarbon generation and entrapment. The reconnaissance surveys and some of the exploration wells drilled in Vindhyan Basin have shown hydrocarbon generation/occurrence (Srivastava et al., 1983, Kumar et al., 2002).

In view of the hydrocarbon potential of the Vindhyan Basin, diagenetic studies of the Bhandar Sandstone have been carried out. These diagenetic modifications will influence reservoir quality and aid in developing future exploration strategies within the basin.

Chapter 2

2. Geological setting

The Vindhyan Basin spreads from Sasaram (Bihar) along the Son River valley in the east to Chittorgarh in the west through Kota, Bundi, Sawai Madhopur districts of Rajasthan (Figure 1). The basin is bounded by the Aravalli-Delhi orogenic belt (2.3–0.8 Ga) in the west, and by the Satpura orogenic belt (1.6–0.85 Ga) in the south and southeast. Low-grade metamorphic rocks of the Mahakoshal (~2.4 Ga) and the Bijawar (~2.1 Ga) supergroups border its eastern margin (Ramakrishnan and Vaidyanadhan 2010). The Bundelkhand Granite (3.3–2.5 Ga), exposed in the centre, divides the basin into the eastern (Son Valley) and western (Rajasthan) sectors and forms the basement in the eastern sector (Prasad 1984; Mondal et al. 2002). The ~2.5 Ga old Berach Granite of the Banded Gneissic Complex -1 (BGC-1), the ~1.8 Ga old Hindoli Group and the Khairmalia volcanics form the basement of the Vindhyan Supergroup in Rajasthan in various sub-basins (Wiedenbeck et al. 1996; Deb et al. 2002; Rao et al. 2013).

Figure 1. Geological map of west-central India showing the location of Vindhyan Supergroup, basement complexes and younger Deccan Traps. The areal extent of four groups of the Vindhyan namely Semri, Kaimur, Rewa and Bhandar Group of rocks are shown. The Great Boundary Fault in the western margin and the Narmada Son Lineament in the eastern margin are also presented (modified after Roy and Jakhar 2002; Ray et al. 2003; Wang et al. 2018). Age data are from Gopalan et al. (1990, 2013), Deb et al. (2002), Mondal et al. (2002), Buick et al. (2006), Ahmad et al. (2008), Malone et al. (2008), Van Lente et al. (2009), Kaur et al. (2011), McKenzie et al. (2011, 2013), Ray et al. (2011), Renne et al. (2015), Tripathy and Singh (2015), and Wang et al. (2018).

Table 2: Stratigraphic classification of the Vindhyan Supergroup after Prasad (1984) and Bhattacharyya (1996). The maximum thickness of various units in meters is given in parentheses

		Son Valley		Rajasthan		
UPPER VINDHYAN	BHANDER GROUP		Shikaoda (Maihar) Sandstone (60)		Bhavpura (Dholpur) Shale (60)	
			Sirbu Shale (176)		Balwan Limestone (120)	
			Bundi Hill Sandstone (60)		Shikaoda Sandstone (130)	
			Lakheri (Bhander) Limestone (54)		Sirbu Shale (185)	
			Ganurgarh Shale (60)		Bundi Hill Sandstone (250)	
	REWA GROUP					Samaria Shale (133)
						Lakheri Limestone (150)
						Ganurgarh Shale (200)
						Taragarh Fort Sandstone (85)
						Jhiri Shale (120)
LOWER VINDHYAN	KAIMUR GROUP		Dhandraul Sandstone (70)		Indergarh Sandstone (60)	
			Mangesar Formation (190)		Panna Shale (120)	
			Bijaigarh Shale (45)			
			Ghaghar Sandstone			
			Susnai Breccia (60)			
	SEMRI GROUP		Sasaram Formation			Kaimur Sandstone with Conglomerate (110)
			Rohtas Subgroup	Bhagwar Shale (210)		unconformity
				Rohtasgarh Limestone		Suket Shale (210)
			Kheinjua Subgroup	Rampur Formation (80)		Nimbahera Limestone (148)
				Salkhan Limestone (8)		Binota Shale (250)
	Mirzapur Subgroup	Koldaha Shale (150)		Kalmia Sandstone (22)		
		Deonar Formation (140)			Palri Shale with Porcellanite (90)	
		Kajrahat Limestone (210)			Sawa Sandstone with Conglomerate (120)	
		Arangi Formation (130)			Bhagwanpura Limestone (90)	
		Deoland Formation (50)			Khardeola Sandstone (360)	
					unconformity	

Aravalli-Delhi supergroups/Berach Granite/Bundelkhand Granite/Jungel volcanics/Bijawar Group of rocks

There is no consensus about the mode of formation and evolution of the Vindhyan basin that is more than 1000 km long and 100 km wide. The two competing tectonic models for the origin of the basin are the intracontinental sag-continental extensional model (e.g. Bhattacharyya 1996 and references therein; Bickford et al. 2017) and the subduction zone-foreland model (e.g. Acharyya 2003; Chakrabarti et al. 2007). The predominantly shallow marine deposits of the Vindhyan Supergroup have been divided into the Semri (Lower Vindhyan), Kaimur, Rewa and Bhander (Upper Vindhyan) groups (Table 2). Individual formations of the groups on both the sectors have been correlated based on lithostratigraphy (Prasad 1984; Soni et al. 1987), however, the correlations of some of the formations remain contentious (Ray 2006).

The Semri Group in Rajasthan (Table 2) is divided into three subgroups namely the Sand, the Lasrawan and the Khorip, from the oldest to the youngest (Prasad 1984). The Sand subgroup began with the deposition of Khardeola Sandstone and ended with the Palri Shale. The Khardeola Sandstone is overlain by the Bhagwanpura Limestone, Sawa Sandstone/Grit and Palri Shale. The Bhagwanpura Limestone formation, though correlated with the ~1721

Ma old Kajarihat Limestone in the Son valley (Sarangi et al. 2004), is highly siliceous and dolomitic unlike the stromatolitic Kajarihat (Banerjee et al. 2007). The upper part of the Sawa Sandstone that grades into the Palri Shale contains silicified tuff (porcellanite) which is believed to be correlatable to the ~1630 Ma old Deonar Porcellanite formation in the Son valley (Ray et al. 2002, 2011; Bickford et al. 2017). The rocks of the Lasrawan subgroup are correlated with that of the Khenjua subgroup in the Son valley (Prasad 1984). The overlying Khorip subgroup, which marks the end of the deposition in the Semri, is made up of three major formations; the Bari or Nimbahera Shale, the Nimbahera Limestone and the Suket Shale. The cumulative thickness of the Semri Group is estimated to be ~ 1.7 km (Soni et al. 1987).

The Upper Vindhyan in Rajasthan began with the deposition of the Kaimur Group, which has only one sedimentary unit, a sandstone, in contrast to six formations of different rock types in the Son valley (Prasad 1984, Table 2). The Kaimur Group in the Son Valley is dated to be ~1210 Ma (Tripathy and Singh 2015) which suggest a depositional hiatus of ~400 million years between the lower and the upper Vindhyan. The overlying Rewa Group is made up of four formations; the Panna Shale, the Indergarh Sandstone, also known as the Lower Rewa Sandstone, the Jhiri Shale and the Taragarh Fort Sandstone or the Upper Rewa Sandstone in stratigraphically ascending order (Table 2). Deposition of the youngest group of the Vindhyan Supergroup, the Bhandar, began with the Ganurgarh Shale which is overlain by the Lakheri Limestone, a ~ 1073 Ma old transgressive sequence (Chakraborty 2004; Gopalan et al. 2013). Unlike its presumed stratigraphic equivalent, the Bhandar Limestone in the Son valley, the Lakheri Limestone is not stromatolitic. The Lakheri Limestone grades into the calcareous Samaria Shale which is found only in the western sector (Rajasthan). The Bundi Hill Sandstone or the Lower Bhandar Sandstone and the Sirbu Shale constitute the lower part of the Bhandar Group (Table 2). The upper part of the Bhandar Group is made up of the Shikaoda Sandstone, which is equivalent to the Maihar Sandstone in the Son valley, the ~800 Ma old Balwan Limestone (Gopalan et al. 2013; George et al. 2018), and the Dholpur Shale. Both the Balwan Limestone and the Dholpur Shale are developed only in the western sector and mark the end of the Vindhyan sedimentation (Table 2).

Chapter 3

3. Detrital mineralogy

Sandstones are composed of mineral grains and rock fragments derived from the natural disintegration and erosion of various rock types. The detrital composition of sandstone is influenced by multiple factors, including tectonic settings (Dickinson and Suczek, 1979; Ingersoll and Suczek, 1979; Valloni and Mazzardi, 1984; Dickinson, 1985; Valloni, 1985), transport mechanisms (Lucchi, 1985; Velbel, 1985), climatic conditions (Suttner, 1974; Mack, 1984; Basu, 1985; Suttner and Dutta, 1986; Grantham and Velbel, 1988; Girty, 1991; Akhtar and Ahmad, 1991; Khan, 1995), and diagenetic processes (McBride, 1985).

Detrital quartz, the principal and dominant component of sandstones, plays a critical role in indicating provenance. Early studies by Sorby (1908) and Mackie (1896) focused on the characteristics of detrital quartz grains. Mackie (1896) classified detrital quartz into four groups based on the nature of their inclusions. Subsequently, Krynine (1940, 1946) introduced a genetic classification system, dividing detrital quartz into three main types: igneous (including plutonic, volcanic, and hydrothermal vein quartz), metamorphic (comprising recrystallized, schistose, and stretched quartz), and reworked sedimentary quartz, based on extinction patterns, inclusions, and grain morphology. Folk (1980) later revised Krynine's category of plutonic quartz to "common quartz," recognizing that quartz from various sources—metamorphic, vein, and others—often exhibits similar characteristics. Additionally, Folk (1980) proposed an empirical classification of detrital quartz grounded in extinction features and inclusions. Blatt and Christie (1963) observed that undulatory extinction alone is not a reliable indicator of quartz provenance. Fuji (1958) identified four varieties of quartz, notably including cryptocrystalline quartz (chert).

Folk and Weaver (1952), Fuji (1958), and Folk (1980) described chert as microcrystalline quartz, cryptocrystalline quartz, and chalcedonic quartz. Pettijohn et al. (1987) further classified chert into four varieties: fine-grained, coarse-grained, specular, and silty. More recently, several researchers have classified chert as a type of rock fragment.

The significance of feldspar has been extensively discussed concerning its relationship to source areas, paleoclimate, and tectonic settings (Martens, 1931; Russell, 1939; Krynine, 1948; Hayes, 1962; Pittman, 1963; Rim Saite, 1967; Field and Pilkey, 1969; Folk, 1980; Pettijohn et al., 1987; Dickinson, 1985). Authigenic feldspar has also been regarded as an indicator of marine depositional environments (Crowley, 1939). The importance of

metamorphic, sedimentary, and volcanic rock fragments was emphasized by Folk (1980), Pettijohn et al. (1987), and Pettijohn (1975).

Although heavy minerals occur as accessory components in typical sandstones, they serve as valuable indicators of the nature of the source rock. In this context, specific heavy mineral assemblages have been identified and linked to their probable source rocks (Boswell, 1933; Krumbein and Pettijohn, 1938; Feo-Codecido, 1956; Fuji, 1958; Iijima, 1959; Okada, 1967; Folk, 1980; Mclarley, 1981; Pettijohn, 1975).

3.1. Methodology

In the present study, the detrital mineral composition of the sandstone was assessed both quantitatively and qualitatively. Thirteen thin sections from the study area (Rasulpur Section) were selected to determine the modal composition and petrographic characteristics of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone. Quantitative analysis of the thin sections was carried out using a Swift automatic point counter attached to a petrographic microscope, with approximately 200–300 grains counted per slide to ensure uniform coverage. The classification of quartz varieties and other framework constituents follows the terminology of Krynine (1940) and Folk (1980). Heavy minerals were separated following the method outlined by Milner (1962).

3.2. Detrital mineral composition

The analyzed sandstone samples are primarily composed of various types of quartz, followed by feldspar, rock fragments, micas, and heavy minerals. The average detrital mineral composition is as follows: monocrystalline quartz (92.79%), polycrystalline recrystallized metamorphic quartz (1.77%), stretched metamorphic quartz (1.23%), feldspar (1.3%), rock fragments (2.22%), and mica and heavy minerals (0.69%) (Table 3).

Quartz

Quartz is the dominant constituent, and its varieties have been identified based on Folk's (1980) classification scheme. The majority of the quartz grains are monocrystalline, accompanied by a smaller proportion of polycrystalline grains. Monocrystalline quartz typically exhibits undulatory extinction, while polycrystalline quartz (Fig 2(B)) displays both sharp and sutured intercrystalline boundaries. The identified varieties of quartz include common quartz, recrystallized metamorphic quartz, and stretched metamorphic quartz.

Table 3 Percentage of detrital minerals of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone

Sample No.	Monocrystalline Quartz	Polycrystalline Quartz		Mica	Chert	Feldspar		Rock Fragment	
	Common	Recrystallized Metamorphic	Stretched Metamorphic			Microcline	Plagioclase	Sedimentary	Metamorphic
R1	92	1	-	-	-	3	2	1	1
R2	91	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
R3	90	3	2	2		1	1	1	-
R4	95	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	1
R5	96	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	-
R6	92	2	2	2		-	-	2	-
R7	89	2	4	-	1	1	2	1	-
R8	95	2	-	1		-	-	1	1
R9	90	3	3	-	1	-	1	-	2
R10	92	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	-
R11	96	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	1
R12	93	1	2	-	2	-	-	2	-
R13	95	2	-	1	-	-	-	1	1
Average	92.79	1.77	1.23	0.69	0.61	0.61	0.69	1	0.61

Common quartz, ranging from 89% to 96% with an average of 92.79%, is the dominant constituent of the studied sandstone. Recrystallised metamorphic quartz contributes between 1% and 3%, averaging 1.77% of the composition. Stretched metamorphic quartz is also present in the studied sandstone, ranging from 0% to 4% and averaging 1.23%.

Feldspar

The detrital feldspar, including both fresh and altered feldspar, occurs in small amounts in the studied sandstone, ranging from 0 to 3% and averaging 0.65%.

Two varieties of feldspar, microcline and plagioclase, have been identified. Altered grains of both types show a dusty appearance (Fig (D)) under plane polarized light and exhibit grey and brown. Their interference colors possess shades of grey and brown.

Chert

The recrystallised metamorphic quartz in the studied sandstone makes up 0 to 02% of its composition, with an average of 0.61%.

Chert grains are typically subrounded to well-rounded and are often smaller than the accompanying quartz grains (Fig 2(A,E)). However, in some instances, they can be equal to or even larger than the quartz grains. Chert also occurs as a cementing material between quartz grains. Chalcedony show radiating, extremely thin fibers under crossed nicols. Common impurities in chert grains include clay, silt, and iron oxide. The presence of chert, similar to multicyclic quartz, suggests a sedimentary or metasedimentary source rock.

Rock fragments

Rock fragments constitute very small component of the studied sandstone, ranging from 0 to 03%, averaging 1.044%.

Besides the previously described chert fragments, sedimentary and metamorphic rock fragments are sparsely distributed within the studied sandstone. Quartzite and schist are the most common varieties of these rock fragments observed.

Sedimentary rock fragments, such as chert, shale, and siltstone, are subrounded to well-rounded and about the same size as the quartz grains. Due to their incompetent nature, the shale fragments occasionally show evidence of squeezing between quartz grains, forming a pseudo matrix.

Figure 2: Microphotographs of Bhandar Sandstone Showing; Monocrystalline quartz and (A) Chert, (B) Polycrystalline quartz, (C) Muscovite flake affected by mechanical compaction, (D) Feldspar grain corroded by iron cement, (E) Chert.

Mica

Mica grains occur as traces in the studied sandstone. They include muscovite and biotite. The percentage ranges from 0 to 02%, averaging at 0.69%.

Randomly distributed as grains, muscovite is commonly found as an altered form of orthoclase. Muscovite and biotite both appear as elongate flakes, varying in size from tiny to large and displaying frayed ends. Mechanical deformation, resulting from pressure by neighboring quartz grains, is sometimes visible in these flakes. Biotite grains are generally brown.

Heavy minerals

In addition to the primary framework components of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone, various heavy minerals are present. These include some opaques as well as zircon, biotite, garnet, hornblende, etc.

3.3. Classification of the sandstone based on folk's scheme

Folk (1980) used a triangular diagram, allotting all types of quartz, including metaquartzite (including chert), to the quartz pole (Q), all single feldspar grains, including granite and gneiss fragments, to the feldspar pole (F), and all other rock fragments such as chert, slate, phyllite, schist, volcanics, limestone, sandstone, and shale to the rock fragment pole (R). In this classification, the percentage of clay matrix, chemically precipitated cements, glauconite, phosphate, fossils, heavy minerals, mica, and similar constituents was ignored. According to Folk's classification scheme, sandstone was divided into seven classes, namely: quartzarenite, subarkose, arkose, lithic arenite, sublitharenite, feldspathic litharenite, and litharenite. For classifying the studied Sandstone, all essential constituents were recalculated to 100 % and allotted to one of the three following poles;

Q- All types of quartz; common quartz, recrystallised metamorphic quartz and stretched metamorphic quartz (including chert)

F- All single feldspar grains plus granite and gneiss fragments.

R- All types of rock fragments; chert, shale, phyllite, schist, siltstone, limestone etc.

The average composition of framework grains of the Bhandar Sandstone is as follows: Quartz- 96.38%, Feldspar – 1.31% and Rock fragments – 1.62% (Table 4). All the samples of the studied sandstone plotted near the Q pole, in the quartzarenite field (Figure 3).

Table 4 Percentage of framework modes of the Bhandar Sandstone			
Sample No.	Qt	F	L
R1	93	5	2
R2	94	2	2
R3	95	2	1
R4	97	2	1
R5	99	0	1
R6	96	0	2
R7	96	3	1
R8	97	0	2
R9	97	1	2
R10	96	2	1
R11	98	0	2
R12	98	0	2
R13	97	0	2
Average %	96.38	1.31	1.62

Figure 3 Classification of the Bhandar Sandstone according to Folk (1980)

Chapter 4

4. Diagenetic evolution

Diagenesis encompasses "all physicochemical, biochemical, and physical processes that modify sediments between deposition and lithification under low temperature and pressure conditions characteristic of surface and near-surface environments" (Chilingar et al., 1967). Principal diagenetic processes include compaction, cementation, authigenesis, recrystallization, replacement, and metasomatism. Diagenesis in clastic rocks is influenced by various factors such as mineralogy, temperature, pressure, water composition, flow rates, dissolution and precipitation kinetics, availability of nucleation sites, porosity, and permeability. Freshly deposited sand represents a porous, non-equilibrium mixture of detrital minerals, which progressively achieves stability through reduction of porosity via compaction and the precipitation of stable authigenic cements or grains.

Diagenesis is locally controlled by fluid migration and the chemical potential of the system. At a regional scale, factors such as tectonic setting of the basin, geothermal gradient, rate and extent of deposition, and basin subsidence become significant controls. In sandstones, diagenetic processes can be broadly categorized into physical and chemical diagenesis. These processes may operate independently, randomly, or simultaneously, responding to the surrounding stress field to achieve chemical equilibrium.

Physical diagenesis of freshly deposited sand involves sediment compaction and pore volume reduction due to pressure. At the sediment-water interface and shallow burial levels, compaction occurs through grain rearrangement processes such as rotation, slippage, ductile deformation, and fracturing of grains without significant dissolution at grain contacts (Houseknecht, 1987). As burial continues, physical compaction increases the number of contacts per grain, eventually transitioning to chemical compaction characterized by intergranular pressure solution at greater depths. Elevated geothermal gradients and pressures lead to dissolution at grain contacts, changing contact types from point to long and interpenetrative forms.

Chemical diagenesis includes reactions resulting in chemical dissolution, corrosion, and cementation. These reactions may commence soon after sand deposition and are influenced by oxidation and reduction processes at the sediment-water or sediment-atmosphere interface. The chemical potential of sediments and pore water chemistry significantly impacts the dissolution of unstable mineral phases and the precipitation of stable phases

within the diagenetic regime. Cementation, one of the primary chemical diagenetic processes, leads to porosity loss by filling pore spaces, though unlike compaction, this loss is reversible. Cementing materials typically include carbonates, silica, iron oxides, or clay minerals, which precipitate under favorable physicochemical conditions, either coating grains or filling voids from pore fluids saturated with these minerals.

The present study of diagenesis in the Upper Bhandar Sandstone primarily focuses on compaction, porosity reduction, and cementation. Compaction is defined as the reduction in volume, expressed either as a percentage of the original void space or the original bulk volume. Although compaction predominantly affects loose, unconsolidated sediments, it can also significantly impact well-cemented rocks, as evidenced by stylolitic contacts. Intergranular pore spaces in clastic sediments are eliminated by tighter grain packing, grain crushing, deformation, fluid expulsion, and, in some cases, grain dissolution. The rates of compaction, porosity and permeability reduction, and fluid expulsion are believed to vary over time, both vertically and laterally across sedimentary basins.

The chemical precipitation of cements within the sedimentary framework depends on the availability of chemical elements delivered by intrastratal or migrating solutions. Understanding the processes of compaction and lithification is crucial for diagenetic studies, as it enables the determination of the direct impacts of compaction and cementation, as well as the temporal relationships between these two processes.

4.1 Methodology

The present study is based on 13 sandstone samples that were prepared into standard petrographic thin sections. For each thin section, between 200 and 250 grains were counted. Standard petrological techniques, utilizing a polarizing microscope, were employed to analyze the thin sections. Authigenic components, including cement and matrix replacement constituents, were counted separately. To reconstruct the original detrital composition of the sandstones, the effects of diagenesis were carefully considered during the counting process. For the study of detrital grain contacts and computation of the contact index, Taylor's (1950) method was employed, while the approach described by Pettijohn et al. (1987) was followed for additional analysis.

4.2 Compaction

Compaction, one of the primary processes of diagenesis, is defined as the expulsion of pore fluids and reduction of pore volume within a sedimentary column due to normal shear and

compressional stresses exerted by the overburden load (Chilingar, 1983). It occurs through four main mechanisms: grain rearrangement, plastic deformation, dissolution, and brittle deformation (Wilson and Staton, 1994). This volume reduction process can be quantified as a percentage of the original void space present in the sediments.

4.3. Grain contact

Grain-to-grain contacts in sediments provide valuable insights into pore space reduction and the compaction history of the rock. The nature of these contacts, along with the contact index, aids in understanding the aggregate packing of sedimentary formations. In this study, the grain contacts of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone were analyzed in thin sections to interpret the compactional history of the formation. Based on Taylor's (1950) classification, the closely packed sandstones exhibit four primary types of grain contacts: point, long (Fig4 (A)), concavo-convex (Fig4 (B)), and sutured (Fig4 (C)). The distribution of these contact types across these 13 samples is summarized in Table 05.

In the case of loosely packed sandstone, some grains do not make contact with adjacent grains; such grains are termed floating grains (F). The average proportions of the different contact types observed in the studied samples are: point contact (22.77%), long contact (58.23%), concavo-convex contact (0.54%), sutured contact (0.23%), and floating grains (14.92%) (Table 05).

The predominance of point and long grain contacts, which together constitute approximately 80% in the studied samples, suggests that the detrital grains were not subjected to significant pressure solution—likely due to either shallow burial or early cementation. According to Taylor (1950), pressure-related effects tend to be minimal or absent in sandstones that experienced early cementation. Nonetheless, signs of both mechanical compaction and pressure solution are evident in the samples. The presence of sutured boundaries and quartz overgrowths points to compaction occurring after cementation. It can therefore be inferred that initial compaction occurred in the early stage, involving grain rotation and adjustment to neighboring grain boundaries, while subsequent compaction took place after the development of cement.

Figure 4 Microphotographs showing;
(A) Point and long contacts, (B) Concavo-convex contact, (C) Sutured contact

Table 5: Packing data for the Bhandar Sandstone.

F= Floating grains, P= Point contact, L= Long contact, Cc= Concavo-convex contact, S= Sutured contact, C.I= Contact Index.

Sample No.	Types of contact										Number of grains in Contact										Contact Index		
	F		P		L		Cc		S		0		1		2		3		4			>4	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		N	%
R1	12	16	9	12	45	68	-	-	11	4	16	10	40	25	63	40	34	22	4	2	1	1	2.3
R2	26	33	10	13	36	52	-	-	8	2	18	20	20	21	34	37	20	22	-	-	-	-	2.1
R3	8	18	4	9	29	71	-	-	4	1	-	-	28	29	40	42	25	26	2	3	-	-	2.5
R4	8	18	6	21	25	57	-	-	5	2	7	6	27	24	39	35	38	34	4	1	-	-	2.62
R5	7	21	5	15	17	58	-	-	4	2	12	10	45	39	32	28	20	17	5	4	1	2	2.15
R6	10	21	6	13	24	57	2	3	6	4	14	13	25	23	35	32	25	23	7	6	2	3	2.63
R7	2	5	14	32	23	54	-	-	5	4	14	11	24	20	45	38	32	27	2	2	2	2	2.39
R8	4	9	10	22	26	63	1	4	4	3	19	17	52	28	75	41	27	13	1	1	-	-	2.13
R9	15	22	21	31	27	38	-	-	4	1	15	12	40	31	47	36	25	14	1	5	2	2	2.2
R10	6	8	25	39	36	57	-	-	8	2	35	18	60	33	70	39	15	10	-	-	-	-	1.85
R11	-	-	21	31	36	56	-	-	10	1	20	13	70	44	55	34	15	9	-	-	-	-	2.31
R12	3	3	35	33	63	59	-	-	4	1	5	3	42	26	65	40	35	22	15	9	-	-	2.28
R13	4	5	22	25	51	67	-	-	10	2	10	7	50	34	70	48	15	10	2	1	-	-	2.14
Average		14.92		22.77		58.23		0.54		2.23													2.28

The **contact index** (CI), defined as the average number of grain-to-grain contacts a grain share with its neighboring grains (Pettijohn et al., 1987), serves as an indicator of the degree of compaction within sediments. In the studied samples, most grains are in contact with two neighboring grains, followed by those in contact with three. The average contact index is relatively high at 2.28 (Table 05), reflecting the predominance of long and point contacts among the framework grains.

The dominance of long and point contacts is attributed to mechanical compaction, which enhances both the contact index and packing density of the sediment framework. Chemical compaction, on the other hand, involves the pressure-induced dissolution of grains along their contacts. This process further increases the framework packing density and leads to progressive changes in the nature of grain contacts—transforming point and long contacts into concavo-convex and eventually sutured contacts.

4.4. Cement

Two types of cementing materials are present in the sandstones of the study area, namely silica and iron oxide. Additionally, a clayey to silty matrix is occasionally observed, which may represent crushed or compacted pelitic rock fragments (Table 06).

Siliceous Cement (SCT)

The silica cement content in the samples ranges from 5% to 12%, with an average of 7% (Table 6). In most samples, silica cement is present as quartz overgrowths that exhibit optical continuity with the detrital quartz grains. These authigenic quartz overgrowths partially occupy the intergranular spaces. The silica cement is present as very well developed (Fig 5(A)), well developed (Fig 5(B)), moderately developed (Fig 5(C)), or poorly developed (Fig 5(D)) around detrital grains. In certain thin sections, the silica cement is primarily composed of chalcedonic and microcrystalline quartz, along with some proto-chalcedonic quartz and mega-quartz. Chalcedonic quartz appears as radiating micro-fibrous aggregates forming fan-shaped structures. Microcrystalline quartz consists of subequant, randomly oriented interlocking grains smaller than 0.06 mm, showing pinpoint birefringence. Proto-chalcedonic quartz, representing the initial stage of silicification, is typically found adjacent to grain boundaries. Mega-quartz occurs as drusy aggregates characterized by straight extinction and a normal refractive index.

Ferruginous Cement (FCT)

Iron oxide cement is present in most of the studied samples, ranging from 0 to 5% with an average of 1.85%. It typically appears as black coatings around detrital grains (Fig 6(B)) and in isolated patches. The thickness of these coatings varies between 10 and 26 microns. Similar iron oxide coatings are also observed around altered and leached feldspar grains (Fig 6(C)), where iron oxide occurs along cleavage traces. In some thin sections, thin iron oxide linings are seen around empty voids, which are interpreted as the remnants of completely leached feldspars. These oversized pore spaces (Fig 6(A)) are likely the result of the destruction and leaching of labile framework grains, most likely feldspars.

Iron oxide in sediments may have formed just after the deposition at the sediment-water interface by was regenerated during burial (Walker, 1974).

Table 6: Cementation and Porosity data for the Bhandar Sandstone.

Fe= Iron oxide cement, Si= Silica cement, M = Matrix, EOP= Existing optical porosity, IGV= Inter Granular Volume, COPL= Compaction Porosity Loss, CEPL= Cementational Porosity Loss, ICompact= Compaction Index

Sample No.	Detrital grains (%)	Cements and Matrix			Total cements	EOP	IGV	COPL	CEPL	ICompact
		Fe	Si	M						
R1	85	-	6	5	6	4	15	35.29	3.88	0.90
R2	87	-	6	3	6	4	13	36.78	3.79	0.91
R3	85	4	5	2	9	4	15	35.29	5.82	0.86
R4	78	4	9	4	13	5	22	29.49	9.17	0.76
R5	83	5	5	3	10	4	17	33.73	6.63	0.84
R6	87	-	6	3	6	4	13	36.78	3.79	0.91
R7	86	-	9	3	9	2	14	35.05	5.76	0.86
R8	90	-	5	4	5	1	10	38.89	3.06	0.93
R9	87	3	5	2	8	3	13	36.78	5.06	0.88
R10	80	1	9	4	10	4	18	32.93	6.71	0.83
R11	77	2	12	4	14	5	23	28.57	10.00	0.74
R12	82	2	6	5	8	5	18	32.93	5.37	0.86
R13	81	3	8	4	11	4	19	32.10	7.47	0.81
Average	83.69	1.85	7.00	3.54	8.85	3.77	16.15	34.28	5.88	0.85

Figure 5: Microphotographs showing;

- (A) Very well-developed overgrowth around detrital grains.
- (B) Well-developed overgrowth around detrital grains.
- (C) Moderately well-developed overgrowth around detrital grains.
- (D) Poorly developed overgrowth around detrital grains

Figure 6: Microphotographs showing:

- (A) Oversized pore spaces (star)
- (B) Detrital quartz grain corroded by iron cement
- (C) Feldspar grain corroded by iron cement.

4.5. Matrix

The studied sandstones contain clayey to silty matrix (Fig 7: A, B) in variable amounts. Compositionally, the matrix consists of fine-grained muscovite, clay, and silt-sized quartz grains. Both syn-depositional and post-depositional matrix types are present. This matrix influences diagenetic processes through its chemical composition and bulk properties, particularly by affecting porosity and permeability through the mechanism of pore occlusion.

Figure 7: Microphotographs (A, B) showing detrital engulfed by clayey to silty matrix.

4.6. Porosity evolution

The original porosity of sediments is altered, either reduced or increased, during diagenesis. In clastic sediments, two primary processes responsible for the reduction in porosity are cementation and compaction. The porosity of sandstones is examined in terms of existing optical porosity (EOP) and intergranular volume (IGV). Heald (1956) defined IGV (formerly referred to as minus cement porosity) as the porosity that would exist if a specimen contained no chemical cement, i.e., the porosity that existed prior to cementation. If the IGV of a sandstone closely approximates the original porosity of freshly deposited sand, it implies that the rock underwent minimal compaction before cementation. Several studies of random packing arrangements in sediments and spherical aggregates provide insight into initial porosities. Beard and Weyl (1973) demonstrated that well-sorted, artificially packed sands have porosities around 39%, while Pryor (1973) found that recent sand bodies exhibit an initial porosity of approximately 45%. Depositional porosity in deltaic sands ranges between 42 and 50 %, as reported by Atkin and McBride (1992).

They took an empirical porosity value equal to 45%, and with this value, they attempted to model the porosity evolution and the relative roles of compaction and cementation. Based on the above-described relationship, intergranular volumes (IGV) of the studied sandstones were computed by adding the volume of cement to the volume of voids present. The volumes of cement and voids were measured in each thin section.

The percentage of existing optical porosity (EOP) in the studied thin sections ranges from 1% to 05%, with an average of 3.77%, while intergranular volume (IGV) ranges from 10% to 23%, averaging at 16.15% (Table 06). The existing optical porosity primarily develops due to the dissolution of iron cement and feldspar grains. The diagenetic evolution of the sandstone comprises two main phases: the initial phase involves a reduction of primary porosity through compaction and cementation processes, followed by a later phase characterized by partial dissolution of rock components, which leads to the development of secondary porosity. The constituents most commonly affected by dissolution include iron cement, feldspar, and rock fragments. This significant dissolution phase typically occurs in relatively deeper subsurface environments. In such settings, most deep reservoir properties undergo considerable modification due to dissolution, resulting in enhanced secondary porosity. The observations in the Upper Bhandar Sandstone indicate that mechanical compaction, which began at the sediment-water interface during early diagenetic conditions, continued progressively and transitioned into chemical compaction in a deeper

burial diagenetic environment. Such diagenetic conditions are typical of rapidly subsiding basins accompanied by the subsequent uplift of peripheral basin margins.

Further, to investigate the influence of compaction to porosity loss, the relationship between Cementation porosity loss (**CEPL**) and Compactional porosity loss (**COPL**) has been used (*see Appendix*). The cross-plot of **COPL** versus **CEPL** (Figure 8) **shows** that the porosity loss is mainly due to compaction.

A plot of **IGV versus cement volume** (Figure 9) indicates that the mechanical compaction played a key role than cementation in destroying the primary porosity of the Bhandar sandstone.

The **Icompact** (*see Appendix*) is a measure of the role of compaction played in the porosity loss. The compaction index (ICOMPACT) (Lundguard 1992) equals 1.0 when all porosity loss is by compaction, and equals 0.0 when all porosity loss is by cementation. The average Icompact value in the studied sandstone is 0.8, which also suggests that the porosity loss is mainly due to compaction.

Figure 8. Cementational porosity loss (CEPL) versus Compactional porosity loss (COPL) for the Sandstone (after Lundguard 1992) indicating that the porosity loss was due to compaction and less cementation.

Figure 9. Houseknecht (1987) diagram showing the relationship between intergranular volume (IGV) and total cement, correlating the primary porosity reduction with cementation and compaction.

Chapter 5

5. Reservoir implication

The reservoir quality of the Neoproterozoic Upper Bhandar Sandstone is significantly influenced by both depositional and diagenetic controls, particularly grain composition, compaction, cementation, and dissolution processes. The dominance of monocrystalline quartz (average 92.79%) indicates a high degree of compositional maturity, which is favorable for preserving primary porosity. However, the porosity of these sandstones has been largely reduced due to mechanical compaction, which plays a more critical role than cementation in destroying primary porosity. This is evident from the average compactional porosity loss (COPL) of 34.28% compared to a cementational porosity loss (CEPL) of 5.88%, and is further supported by a high compaction index ($I_{\text{Compact}} = 0.85$), suggesting that most porosity loss occurred prior to significant cementation. Moreover, a plot of IGV versus cement volume (Figure 6) indicates that mechanical compaction played a more dominant role than cementation in reducing primary porosity in the Bhandar Sandstone.

Grain-to-grain contact analysis shows a dominance of long (58.23%) and point contacts (22.77%), indicating moderate to high degrees of mechanical compaction. Optical evidence also reveals bending and fracturing of mica and the formation of pseudomatrix, highlighting the mechanical deformation of grains. Additionally, the development of a silty to clayey matrix, partly resulting from the compaction of pelitic fragments, contributes to further reduction in porosity and permeability.

Chemical compaction, though less dominant, is evidenced by the presence of silica overgrowths and pressure-solution features. Silica cementation, primarily as authigenic quartz overgrowths, occurs in various degrees—from very well developed to poorly developed—and is a major factor in pore throat occlusion. In certain thin sections, chalcedonic, microcrystalline, proto-chalcedonic, and mega-quartz are also observed. Iron oxide cements, though less abundant (average 1.85%), also contribute to blocking pore spaces. Carbonate cementation is not widely reported in the studied samples, indicating limited influence on reservoir quality.

The existing optical porosity (EOP) averages 3.77%, while the intergranular volume (IGV) averages 16.15%, confirming that significant primary porosity has been lost. However, secondary porosity has developed, primarily through the dissolution of feldspar and iron

cement during deeper burial or uplift phases. Oversized pore spaces resulting from feldspar leaching are evident in thin sections, suggesting localized enhancement of reservoir quality. Overall, the reservoir quality of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone is moderate and variable. While initial compositional maturity and framework stability supported porosity retention, intense mechanical compaction and silica cementation substantially reduced porosity and permeability. Nevertheless, secondary porosity due to feldspar dissolution and limited cementation in certain intervals presents potential "sweet spots" for reservoir development.

Chapter 6

6. Summary and conclusions

The Vindhyan basin, one of the largest Meso-Neoproterozoic basins of the Indian Peninsula, extends over a strike length of more than 162,000 km² in a NE-SW direction. Bordered by the Aravalli-Delhi orogenic belt to the west, the Son-Narmada lineament to the southwest, and the Satpura orogenic belt to the southeast, the basin exhibits the geometry of a half graben. The basin reaches its greatest depth towards the southwest, near the Son-Narmada lineament, and gradually shallows towards the northwest, near the Bundelkhand Massif. The Upper Bhandar Sandstone Formation, which defines the northern extension of the Vindhyan Basin, is characterized by a fossil graben with over 4500 meters of thick metasedimentary successions.

In this study, the diagenetic evolution of the Bhandar Sandstone was investigated by examining its petrography and diagenetic aspects. A total of 13 samples were selected for analysis, and standard petrographic thin sections were prepared and stained with cobalt nitrate for potassium feldspar recognition. Approximately 250 to 300 grains per thin section were counted, and traditional classification methods (Ingersoll et al., 1984) were used to tabulate grain types. The study employed standard petrological techniques using a polarizing microscope to describe the thin sections, and heavy mineral separation followed Carver (1971), with identification based on Krumbein and Pettijohn (1938) and Milner (1962). The contact index was calculated using the method of Taylor (1950) and Pettijohn et al. (1987).

The diagenetic processes in the sandstones were examined to assess the modification of the original detrital composition. The detrital mineralogy of the sandstones, including both light and heavy minerals, was studied for petrographic classification and diagenetic evolution. According to the classification scheme of Folk (1980), the Upper Bhandar Sandstone is predominantly a quartzarenite, with quartz being the dominant framework grain, followed by feldspar, rock fragments, micas, and heavy minerals. The majority of the quartz grains are monocrystalline, exhibiting undulatory extinction, while polycrystalline quartz shows sharp and sutured intercrystalline boundaries. Feldspar minerals, including plagioclase and microcline, are present in both fresh and altered varieties. Micas, particularly biotite and large flakes of muscovite, are also observed. Rock fragments in the sandstone include chert, shale, schist, and phyllite. The average detrital

mineralogy of the studied sandstones consists of 92.79% monocrystalline quartz, 1.77% polycrystalline recrystallized metamorphic quartz, 1.23% stretched metamorphic quartz, 1.3% feldspar, 2.22% rock fragments, and 0.69% mica and heavy minerals. The detrital grains are within the sand size range, and the presence of feldspar and rock fragments suggests prolonged reworking and the influence of high-gradient streams within the basin. The occurrence of zircon, tourmaline, and rutile indicates an origin from igneous (plutonic) source rocks, while the presence of epidote, garnet, and staurolite points to a source from metamorphic rocks. Thus, the suite of heavy minerals suggests a mixed provenance, likely from Precambrian metasediments, the Bundelkhand Massifs, and the granite-gneiss of the Aravalli-Delhi Supergroup.

The sandstones also contain a silty and clayey matrix, which is composed mainly of fine-grained monocrystalline quartz, muscovite, and feldspar grains. The framework grains of the Upper Bhandar Sandstone exhibit primarily long contacts (58.23%), followed by point contacts (22.77%), which explains the high contact index observed in the samples. Porosity was studied in terms of optical porosity (EOP) and intergranular volume (IGV), with average values of 3.77% and 16.15%, respectively. The primary porosity of the sandstone has been reduced mainly due to compaction, which was influenced by the roundness of the detrital particles. The absence of significant early cementation allowed for the compaction to dominate the porosity loss.

The relationship between cementation porosity loss (CEPL) and compactional porosity loss (COPL) was also examined. The cross-plot of COPL versus CEPL indicated that porosity loss in these sandstones is primarily due to compaction, with average values of 5.88% for CEPL and 34.28% for COPL. A major diagenetic event observed in the sandstones was the alteration and dissolution of feldspar grains. The feldspar grains exhibit different stages of alteration, with some completely dissolved, leading to the formation of oversize pores. This dissolution and loss of feldspar most likely occurred in the shallow weathering zone, as evidenced by the absence of illitization and the shallow depth of burial in the region.

In conclusion, the Upper Bhandar Sandstone exhibits a complex diagenetic history, with significant compaction and feldspar dissolution as key processes. The study of its petrography and diagenetic aspects provides valuable insights into the provenance and diagenetic evolution of these sandstones, contributing to a better understanding of the geological history of the Vindhyan basin.

Chapter 7

7. Appendix

Contact Index (C) = the average no of contacts per grain irrespective of nature of contacts.

Intergranular Volume (IGV)= the sum of remaining pore spaces, volume of pore filling cements and depositional matrix (Paxton et al., 2002). This is equivalent to the term “pre-cement primary porosity” and the term minus-cement porosity commonly found in earlier publications.

Compaction Porosity Loss (COPL) = amount of original porosity lost by compactional processes (expressed as a percentage of the original rock volume).

$$COPL = P_i \frac{(100 - P_i) \times IGV}{100 - IGV}$$

Where P_i is the initial depositional porosity (=45%) and IGV is Intergranular Volume {Sum of remaining pore spaces, volume of pore filling cements and depositional matrix (Paxton et al., 202002)}

$$Cementational Porosity Loss (CEPL) = (P_i - COPL) \times \frac{T_c}{IGV}$$

Where T_c is total cement and IGV is Intergranular Volume

Compaction Index (ICompact) = the fractional ratio of compactional porosity loss (COPL) to the sum of Compactional (COPL) and Cementational (CEPL) porosity loss.

$$ICompact = \frac{COPL}{COPL + CEPL}$$

*after Lundguard 1992

Chapter 8

8. References

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